

The Role of Gradient of the Logarithm of Density in the Quantum Mechanics, Classical Mechanics, the Euler Equation, Equilibrium Statistical Mechanics and Brownian Motion

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It is interesting to note that $d/dx [\ln(d(x))]$ where $d(x)$ is the spatial density, plays a central role in the time-independent Schrodinger equation, classical mechanics, the Euler equation, equilibrium statistical mechanics and Brownian motion and in all cases, even the quantum one, is related to force as $-d/dx V(x)$, where $V(x)$ is the potential. In this note, we try to examine the role of $d/dx [\ln(d(x))]$, and in particular try to see how quantum mechanics is related to classical and fluid mechanics and how it differs.

The Role of $d/dx [\ln(d(x))]$ In Classical Mechanics

In classical mechanics, the density is equated to $1/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the velocity obtained from $.5m v(x)*v(x) + V(x) = E$ (1). In such a case, one can show that:

$$d/dx [\ln(d(x))] (m v(x)*v(x)) = - [d/dx V(x)] d(x) \text{ where } -d/dx V(x) = F(x) \text{ force}$$

Brownian Motion

From (2) using ideas from Einstein, the result for Brownian motion is:

$F(x)/mb = D d/dx \ln(d(x))$ ((1)) where D , m and b are constants and D is proportional to temperature.

With Brownian motion, it is interesting to note that one uses a diffusion equation in the derivation of ((1)) and states that $\text{grad}(d(x))$ represents the number of particles moving through an area. This is an interesting picture, because in the classical mechanical case above it as if one has a diffusion of kinetic energy (2)(.5)m $v(x)*v(x) d/dx(d(x))$.

Euler Equation

From (3), the Euler equation is given as:

$$d/dx [.5u*u + P(x)/d(x) + V(x)/m] = 0 \text{ where } P(x) = d(x) kT \text{ and } u(x) \text{ equals flow velocity}$$

Thus, $P(x)/d(x) = d/dx \ln(d(x))$ and $-d/dx V(x) = F(x)$. If one set $u(x)$ to become very low or zero one has:

$T/m \frac{d}{dx} \ln(d(x)) = 1/m F(x)$ which yields an $\exp(-V(x)/T)$, the classical statistical mechanical equilibrium result.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

We have seen from the Euler equation, that one can obtain the statistical mechanical equilibrium case if $u(x)$ flow velocity, is zero. Alternatively, one can maximize Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint on the average potential energy:

Extremize $-\int d(x) \ln(d(x)) + (1/T) \int d(x) V(x)$ where $1/T$ is a Lagrange multiplier so

$$\ln(d(x)) = C_1 - (1/T) V(x) \quad \text{which leads to an } \exp(-V(x)/T) \text{ result. ((2))}$$

Now, one can take the gradient of ((2)) to obtain the Euler equation result for $u=0$, i.e.

$$T \frac{d}{dx} \ln(d(x)) = - \frac{d}{dx} V(x) \quad ((3))$$

Here one has a kind of "Temperature" flux given by the left hand side of ((3)) whereas in classical mechanics, it was a kinetic energy flux.

Quantum Mechanics

In quantum mechanics, matters are very different as one has a spatial density $d(x) = C \sin(kx)\cos(kx)$ even for a particle in a box with no potential (except at the walls). Thus, it seems that one is not dealing with a point particle, but rather with a zitterbewegung type of object which may have some internal motion, i.e. is bouncing back and forth while moving forward with velocity v (4). This seems to be important for the treatment of quantum mechanics. Nevertheless, it also seems that quantum mechanics (the time-independent Schrodinger equation) can be expressed in a form that makes it look similar to the " $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(d(x))$ related to $-\frac{d}{dx} V(x)$ " equation listed above. To see this, consider:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\frac{1}{2m} \right) W(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \{ (E - V(x)) d(x) \} = \frac{d}{dx} \{ .5mv(x)v(x) d(x) \}$$

Where $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. Then, one has:

$$-.5m v(x)v(x) [.5 \frac{d}{dx} \ln(d(x))] + (-1/2m)(1/W(x)) (\frac{d}{dx})^3 W(x) = -\frac{d}{dx} V(x) \quad ((4))$$

This is an interesting result, because the time-independent quantum mechanical equation fits the $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(dx)$ pattern, resembling the classical mechanical equation the closest, although in the case of an oscillator potential and a ground state $W(x)$, it will actually lead to classical statistical mechanical form. The main difference is the extra term:

$$(1/W(x)) (d/dx)^3 W(x)$$

which is proportional to a kind of average value of k^3 . The factor on the first term is also different.

To try to understand the meaning of this, consider the case in which $d/dx V(x)=0$, i.e. there is no force. A classical particle will bounce back and forth in a box with $d(x)=\text{constant}$ so $d/dx \ln(d(x)) = 0$. For the quantum mechanical case, there is a density even for a particle in a box. The ground state $d(x)=C \sin(kx)\sin(kx)$.

Thus, in order to have the force become zero, there must be a second term to counteract this term which is what $(1/W(x)) (d/dx)^3 W(x)$ does. Thus, even though $-.5m v(x)v(x) [.5 d/dx \ln(d(x))]$ is of the same form as the classical result, the quantum mechanical density is different because one is dealing with zitterbewegung particles. The $(1/W(x)) (d/dx)^3 W(x)$ terms deals with this. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note, how the time independent Schrodinger equation is similar to the classical and statistical mechanical cases.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to show that $B(x) d/dx [\ln(d(x))]$ where $B(x)$ is a function and $d(x)$, the density, is related to $-d/dx V(x)$, the force, for Brownian motion, classical mechanics, the Euler equation of fluid flow, classical statistical mechanics and even quantum mechanics. In quantum mechanics there is an extra term to deal with the fact that one is dealing with zitterbewegung particles.

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